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Wasting of Critical Raw Materials in Batteries for Single-Use E-Cigarettes

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This paper focuses on the use of lithium-ion batteries in single-use e-cigarettes, examining their material composition and impact on the waste of critical raw materials. Lithium-ion secondary batteries are currently the most widely used battery type worldwide. Their development has paved the way for a variety of applications, including drones, smartphones, and electromobility. It has been discovered that secondary lithium-ion cells, which contain valuable materials, are being used in single-use applications. The consumption of these single-use e-cigarettes, which employ lithium-ion cells with a potential lifespan of several hundred cycles if reused, leads to the waste of critical and strategic raw materials in the Czech Republic alone. These discarded materials could have been used to manufacture several thousand battery packs for electric vehicles annually.

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1. Introduction

With the rapid growth of the Li-ion battery market, the demand for the materials from which they are made is steadily increasing. This demand is mainly driven by the planned transition to electric vehicles, which use large amounts of elements such as lithium, nickel, cobalt, manganese, aluminium, and copper in their battery packs. Most of these materials are classified as Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) or Strategic Raw Materials (SRMs) by the European Union.^{[1],[2]} The EU seeks to ensure a sustainable supply of these materials and their circular economy to meet its climate objective and secure industrial competitiveness.^{[2],[3]} However, in addition to the increased use of these battery materials in the growing electromobility, other applications whose consumption of CRMs is not readily apparent at first glance, such as e-cigarettes, have emerged in recent years.

Tobacco use is considered one of the most serious but preventable causes of death and chronic non-infectious diseases in most developed countries. Although the number of tobacco users in the Czech Republic has been slowly declining since 2012, according to the annual survey of the State Health Authority (NAUTA), approximately 24.6% of the total population were tobacco smokers in 2023.^[4] According to the Czech project "Česko v datech" (the Czech Republic in data), the Czech Republic ranks 7th in the world in cigarette consumption, with an average of over 2,400 cigarettes a year for every person above the age of 15.^[4] Considering the age structure of the Czech population, 83.83% (9.08 million) of the total population consists of people over the age of 15.^[6] This implies that approximately 21.8 billion cigarettes are smoked annually in the Czech Republic. However, according to the manufacturers (JT International), the overall tobacco market has been over the last few years relatively stable, with just under 23 billion cigarettes (and their equivalents) sold annually, which translates into approximately 2600 cigarettes (and their equivalents) consumed annually by every person above the age of

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15.^[7] Similar data are also given in the Report on Tobacco, Nicotine, and Related Products in the Czech Republic, which puts the per capita consumption of cigarettes in 2009-2020 in the range of 1,894-2,071.^[8] This indicates that the average smoker consumes approximately 479-528 packs of cigarettes per year.

Since 2017, the Czech Republic has had a total ban on smoking (Act No.65/2017 Coll.) in all restaurants, bars, cafés, wine bars, and other food service establishments (the ban does not apply to e-cigarettes and hookahs), and a ban on smoking at public transport stops (also applies to e-cigarettes), ban on smoking in zoos (does not apply to e-cigarettes), ban on smoking in schools, hospitals, means of public transport, sports halls, and children's playgrounds, entertainment facilities and shopping centres (also applies to e-cigarettes).^[8] The implementation of this law has caused a significant increase in the popularity of cigarette alternatives, which are in many aspects not covered by it.

A popular alternative to cigarette smoking is electronic cigarettes (e-cigarettes), also called vaporizers or electronic nicotine delivery systems (ENDS). E-cigarettes convert e-liquid (propylene glycol/glycerol/nicotine and other substances) into aerosol (vapor). E-cigarettes come in a variety of shapes and sizes, but all contain a battery, a heating element, and a liquid tank.^[9] They can be divided into 3 main categories: tanks/mods, rechargeable e-cigarettes (cartridges/pods), and single-use e-cigarettes. According to Tobacco Atlas, the market share of each type of e-cigarette varies by country of sale and year.^[10] However, in the U.S., for example, single-use e-cigarettes accounted for 53.7% of the e-cigarette market in 2021 and as much as 55.3% in 2022.^{[10],[11]} Most single-use e-cigarettes contain a battery with an average capacity of around 400 mAh and can last roughly 500-600 puffs.^[12] On average, they contain 2 ml of e-liquid (maximum is 10 ml) with a nicotine strength of up to 20 mg/ml, which means that one single-use e-cigarette is the approximate equivalent of a pack of cigarettes.^[8] According to an

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annual survey by the State Health Authority, approximately 11.1% of respondents smoke e-cigarettes at least once a month, while 6.1% use e-cigarettes daily, and 45.0% of e-cigarette users use single-use e-cigarettes.^[4] According to the 2023 survey conducted by Ecobat, the disposal of batteries in waste bins is a common practice across various age demographics. The data indicates that 66.7% of the population aged between 18-26 years, 55.6% of the population aged between 27-35 years, 61.1% of the population aged between 36-44 years, and 46.2% of the population aged between 45-53 years, dispose of their e-cigarettes in waste bins.^[13] This highlights a significant environmental concern regarding the proper disposal and recycling of batteries.

As no single material suits every application, ongoing efforts are dedicated to the development of new cathode materials. Presently, the commonly employed cathode materials encompass LiCoO_2 (LCO), $\text{LiNi}_x\text{Mn}_y\text{Co}_{1-x-y}\text{O}_2$ (NMC), $\text{LiNi}_x\text{Co}_y\text{Al}_{1-x-y}\text{O}_2$ (NCA), LiFePO_4 (LFP), and LiMn_2O_4 (LMO).^[14] The limitations of LCO (Lithium Cobalt Oxide) technology are primarily due to the limited supply and high cost of cobalt.^[15] Additionally, the safety of this material is compromised due to its poor thermal stability. This is particularly evident during overcharging, as de-lithiated LCO is notably unstable, and thermal exhaustion can occur.^[16] In contrast, NMC represents a new generation of cathode materials offering increased specific capacity, extended lifespan, enhanced safety features, and reduced cost, attributed to its partial cobalt content.^[17] NCA displays the highest specific power. However, a significant disadvantage is its below-average cycling performance and thermal stability.^[18] Among the listed cathode materials, LFP stands out with the lowest voltage and moderate capacity. However, it compensates with excellent environmental impact, low cost, and remarkable stability and safety features.^[19] Another economically viable and environmentally friendly material is LMO. However, its limited capacity and rapid capacity reduction during cycling hinder its broader commercial

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application, such as in electric vehicles (EVs). Efforts are underway to improve the capacity and cycling characteristics of LMO as a cathode material.^[20] The specific material composition of the battery depends mainly on the type of application. Naturally, energy-intensive applications such as electric vehicles prefer materials with high energy density such as NMC and NCA, whereas in less energy-intensive applications (e.g. power tools), materials such as LFP and LMO are more commonly used.

In this paper, we focused on identifying the types of Li-ion batteries used and their composition within single-use e-cigarettes. Samples of six different single-use e-cigarettes were analysed, their electrochemical properties were measured and then their composition was determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). The amount of materials used annually within the country in these cigarettes could be used to produce dozens of electric cars and the presence of expensive elements such as nickel and cobalt was detected.

2. Experimental

A variety of single-use cigarettes were disassembled (e.g. the disassembled e-cigarette Elfbar 600 shown in **Figure 1**), from which the batteries were subsequently extracted and subjected to measurements. The discharge characteristics of dozens of batteries from single-use e-cigarettes were measured and the measured capacity was compared with the capacity indicated on the battery packaging. Based on the shape of the discharge curves, a representative sample of 6 batteries was selected for further analysis. The selected batteries were from e-cigarettes made by WAKA, VENIX, SALT, LIO NANO, ELFBAR, and MOTI PIIN. Additionally, one battery from a rechargeable cartridge e-cigarette (RELX Essential) was analyzed for comparison.

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Figure 1. Disassembled single-use e-cigarette.

All electrochemical measurements were conducted using a Biologic VMP3 potentiostat with EC-Lab software. Sample No.1 cell (VENIX) was subjected to a long-term stability and cyclability test, which involved cycling at 0,2C for at least 100 cycles to determine if the batteries in single-use e-cigarettes have the potential to be reused. Afterward, all analyzed batteries were disassembled, and the individual components were weighed to analyze their composition, with a particular focus on the cathode material. A sample measuring 5x5 mm was cut from the cathode material using scissors, then attached to a copper plate using double-sided carbon tape and placed in a sample holder. The sample was polished using the CleanMill Broad Ion Beam System (Thermo Fisher Scientific) at 16 kV in cross-sectional mode. Finally, the sample was examined using an Apreo 2 SEM system (Thermo Fisher Scientific) equipped with EDS analysis and ColorSEM Technology.

3. Results and discussions

Lithium-ion batteries were extracted from each e-cigarette. These batteries, along with their capacities and stored energy as specified by their respective manufacturers, are listed in Table

1.

3.1. Electrochemical properties

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The individual discharge characteristics for the cells under test are shown in Figure 2a. The measured characteristics vary, particularly in the discharge curves, most likely due to differences in the composition of the cathode materials. The measured capacities and energies are presented in Table 1. In most cases, the measured capacity is higher than the nominal capacity.

Table 1. Basic characteristics of batteries from single-use e-cigarettes.

Samples	Trade label	Nominal capacity [mAh]	Measured capacity [mAh]	Nominal voltage [V]	Nominal energy [Wh]
Sample No.1	VENIX	400	416.2	3.7	1.480
Sample No.2	ELFBAR 600	550	568.8	3.7	2.035
Sample No.3	WAKA	400	395.4	3.7	1.480
Sample No.4	MOTI PIIN	320	332.0	3.7	1.184
Sample No.5	SALT	400	417.8	3.7	1.480
Sample No.6	LIO NANO	500	413.8	3.7	1.850
Average		428.3	424.0	3.7	1.585

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Figure 2. (a) Discharge characteristics of analysed batteries, (b) Capacity fade of Sample No.1 (VENIX) battery during cycling at 0.2 C

All analyzed batteries were cycled in a potential window of 2.7–4.2 V (Figure 2a). Sample No.1 (VENIX) was cycled a minimum of 100 cycles to check the reusability of the battery (see Figure 2b). The initial capacity of Sample No.1 (VENIX) was measured to be around 421 mAh, while the nominal capacity stated by the manufacturer is 400 mAh. After 100 cycles, the capacity fell to 384 mAh, which means that the capacity loss between the first and 100th cycle was 8.8%.

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As can be seen from Figure 2b, the capacity loss is almost linear. Coulombic efficiency was constantly around 100% throughout the cycling.

3.2. Battery compositions

All samples were disassembled into individual parts and weighed. The electrolyte weight ratio was determined by the difference between the total cell weight and the weight of the dried components. The individual cathode samples were subjected to material analysis to determine the cathode material.

As evident from Figure 3a, the majority of the weight of Sample No.1 (VENIX) is made up of electrode materials. Of this, the largest part (45.9%) corresponds to the cathode, while 5.3% of the total weight is made up of the Al collector. The second largest part (31.9%) corresponds to the anode, while 10.6% of the total weight belongs to the Cu collector. The remaining nearly one-quarter of the weight is made up of other components such as electrolyte (9.1%), separator (7.2%), casing (4.2%), and other plastic parts (1.6%). Since it was not possible to determine the exact amount and composition of the electrolyte in our conditions, the weight of the electrolyte was determined as the difference between the total weight of the whole battery and all its components after drying. Based on the calculation, it was found that the electrolyte is responsible for approximately 9.1% of the total weight of the battery.

Subsequently, structural and elemental analyses (SEM and EDS analyses) were performed. Figure 3b shows the structure of the cathode material of Sample No.1 (VENIX), while Figure 3c-e show the distribution of selected elements in the cathode material. The figures show that there are large grains of LMO and a few smaller grains of NMC in the cathode material. The EDS analysis of the cathode material cross-section of Sample No.1 (VENIX) shows that only 1.4% of the cathode material consists of Co (Figure 3c), 48.4% of the cathode material consists

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of Mn (Figure 3d) and 4.0% consists of Ni (Figure 3e). According to the analyses, the cathode material consists of a mix of LMO and NMC in a weight ratio of 90% LMO to 10% NMC. The mass distribution in the cathode material corresponds to 2.283 g of Mn, 0.066 g of Co, and 0.189 g of Ni. The observed material composition of the cathode corresponds to the measured discharge characteristic of Sample No.1 (VENIX). The voltage of Sample No.1 (VENIX) is slightly higher compared to the other samples, which corresponds to the higher LMO content, which is typically characterized by a higher potential than NMC. In terms of the content of critical raw materials, a single-use battery should contain as little as possible. It is more advantageous that the cathode material of Sample No.1 (VENIX) is largely made up of Mn and the amount of Co and Ni is relatively small.

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Figure 3. (a) Bill of material of Sample No.1 cell, (b) SEM image of cathode material - cross-sectional view, (c) EDS image of Cobalt, (d) EDS image of Manganese, (e) EDS image of Nickel

For Sample No.2 (ELFBAR), up to 46.3% of the mass of the cell is represented by the cathode, with the cathode material accounting for 41.9% and the Al collector for 4.4% (see Figure 4a). The anode accounts for only 33.6% of the total cell weight, with 22.5% made up of the anode material and 11.1% of the Cu collector. The remaining weight of the cell includes an electrolyte,

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separator (5.8%), casing (4.7%), and other plastic parts (2.7%). The electrolyte was calculated to constitute 6.9% of the cell's total weight.

From the surface and elemental analysis of the cross-section of the cathode material of Sample No.2 (ELFBAR) (see Figure 4b,c), it can be seen that up to 60.5% of the cathode material consists of Co. The amount of cobalt thus corresponds to 2,783 g of the total 4,639 g of cathode material. No traces of Mn and Ni were found in the cathode material, however, there were traces of Zn, which was probably used for surface treatment. The analysis results indicate that Sample No.2 (ELFBAR) is composed of LCO material. From both an ecological and economical perspective, this material is highly unsuitable for use in single-use applications.

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Figure 4. (a) Bill of material of Sample No.2 cell, (b) SEM image of cathode material - cross-sectional view, (c) EDS image of Cobalt, (d) EDS image of Manganese, (e) EDS image of Nickel

In the case of Sample No.3 (WAKA), 44.7% of the cell weight is accounted for by the cathode and 34.2% by the anode (see Figure 5a). The cathode material constitutes 39.9% of the cell's weight, while the Al collector accounts for 4.8%. The anode material accounts for 23.1% of the total weight of the cell, and the Cu collector accounts for 11.1%. The remaining 21.1% is composed of other cell components. These include the electrolyte (8.1%), casing (5.4%), separator (5.2%), and other plastics (2.3%).

Based on the structural and elemental analysis of Sample No.3 (WAKA), it is evident that the cathode material consists of a mix of two types of grains (see Figure 5b-e). Perfectly rounded LCO grains and also smaller NMC grains which are more porous and not as uniform around the edges. EDS analysis of a cross-section of the cathode material of Sample No.3 (WAKA) showed that the cathode material contained 38.5% Co (Figure 5c), 15.9% Mn (Figure 5d) and 14.3% Ni (Figure 5e). The weight distribution in the cathode material corresponds to 0.447 g Mn, 1.194 g Co, and 0.443 g Ni. The EDS analysis also showed 0.8 % of W, which we consider to be pollution from the manufacturing process. The remaining cathode material consists of C, O, and electrolyte residues. The analysis results show that the cathode material of Sample No.3 (WAKA) is a mixture of NMC 532 and pure LCO in a weight ratio of 50% NMC and 50% LCO. Doping the LCO with NMC material increases the stability and safety of the cathode material during cycling, but the content of elements such as Ni and Co is still high, which is not suitable for single-use applications.

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Figure 5. (a) Bill of material of Sample No.3 cell, (b) SEM image of cathode material - cross-sectional view, (c) EDS image of Cobalt, (d) EDS image of Manganese, (e) EDS image of Nickel

As illustrated in Figure 6a, the cathode material in Sample No. 4 (MOTI PIIN) constitutes 32.6% of the total cell weight, and the Al collector makes up 4.8% of the total weight. The anode material accounts for 27.8% of the total cell weight, and the Cu collector corresponds to 10.4% of the total weight. The remaining weight of the cell is composed of a separator (8.9%),

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casing (5.1%), and other plastic parts (3.1%). The electrolyte content was determined to be 7.2% of the total weight.

Analyses of Sample No. 4 (MOTI PIIN) showed that there are two types of grains in the cathode material. Perfectly rounded LCO grains and also smaller NMC grains which are more porous and not as uniform around the edges. EDS analysis of the cathode cross-section revealed that the cathode material of Sample No. 4 (MOTI PIIN) contains 38.9% Co (Figure 6c), 14.9% Mn (Figure 6d), and 13.4% Ni (Figure 6e). Similar to Sample No. 3 (WAKA), the cathode material of Sample No. 4 (MOTI PIIN) is a blend of NMC 532 and pure LCO, with a weight distribution of 50% NMC and 50% LCO. The element weight distribution corresponds to 0.253 g of Mn, 0.661 g of Co, and 0.228 g of Ni. The remainder of the cathode material consists of C, O, and electrolyte residues. The discharge characteristics shown in Figure 2a further corroborate the identical material composition of samples No. 3 (WAKA) and No. 4 (MOTI PIIN). As in the case of Sample No. 3, Sample No. 4 cell is also not suitable for use in a single-use application.

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Figure 6. (a) Bill of material of Sample No.4 cell, (b) SEM image of cathode material - cross-sectional view, (c) EDS image of Cobalt, (d) EDS image of Manganese, (e) EDS image of Nickel

In Sample No. 5 (SALT) cell, the cathode is responsible for 43.7% of the total cell weight, while the Al collector is responsible for 5.5% (Figure 7a). The anode represents 33.3% of the total weight, with 10.7% made up of the copper current collector. The casing accounts for 7.2% of the cell's total weight, while the separator and other plastic parts contribute 5.8% and 1.9%, respectively. Electrolyte content was determined to be 8.0 %.

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SEM and EDS analyses of Sample No. 5 (SALT) (Figure 7b-e) show that the cathode material of Sample No. 5 is composed of three types of grains. Large porous LMO grains, small and rounded LCO grains, and then larger grains of Ni-rich material probably composed of LiNiO_2 (LNO) with small doping of Mn and Co. EDS analysis of the cathode cross-section revealed that the cathode material contains 16.4% Co (Figure 7c), 26.7 % Mn (Figure 7d) and 24.1% Ni (Figure 7e). The weight distribution in the cathode material corresponds to 0.747 g of Mn, 0.459 g of Co, and 0.674 g of Ni. The rest of the cathode material is made up of C, O, and the residual electrolyte. The largest part of the cathode material of Sample No. 5 (SALT) is composed of LMO material, but there is also a large part of LCO and Ni-rich material. Overall, both Ni and Co are abundant in the cathode material. The battery is thus less suitable for single-use applications.

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Figure 7. (a) Bill of material of Sample No.5 cell, (b) SEM image of cathode material - cross-sectional view, (c) EDS image of Cobalt, (d) EDS image of Manganese, (e) EDS image of Nickel

The electrode materials also form the bulk of the cell in the case of Sample No.6 (LIO NANO), with the cathode representing up to 42.5% (5.5% being the Al collector) and the anode representing about 33.6% (10.6% being the Cu collector). The bill of materials is depicted in Figure 8a.

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Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.b shows an SEM image of the cathode material of the Sample No.6 (LIO NANO) cell. Two types of grains can be observed in the image. Perfectly rounded LCO grains and also NMC grains which are more porous and not as smooth around the perimeter. The cathode material is most probably a blend of NMC 532 and pure LCO in weight distribution of 53 % NMC and 47 % LCO. EDS analysis of the cathode cross-section revealed that the cathode material contains 11.4 % Mn, whose EDS map is shown in **Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.d**, 30.2 % Co (Figure 8c), and 18.5 % Ni (**Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.e**). The weight distribution in the cathode material corresponds to 0.338 g of Mn, 0.896 g of Co, and 0.549 g of Ni. EDS analysis also showed 1 % of W, which is likely to be contamination from the manufacturing process. The remainder of the cathode material consists of C, O, and electrolyte residues. Having 53% of NMC in the mix improves the stability and safety of the cathode material during cycling. However, the high Co content and significant Ni representation make the battery less suitable for a single-use application.

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Figure 8. (a) Bill of material of Sample No.6 cell, (b) SEM image of cathode material - cross-sectional view, (c) EDS image of Cobalt, (d) EDS image of Manganese, (e) EDS image of Nickel

Sample No.7 (RELX) with a nominal capacity of 350 mAh was obtained from a rechargeable e-cigarette that had been previously used for several months (more than 6 months). The total number of recharge cycles is thus unknown. After disassembling the e-cigarette and subjecting the battery to electrochemical analyses, the battery was found to have a capacity of 359.5 mAh. The measurements show that despite previous prolonged use (several months), the measured

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battery capacity is still above the nominal capacity. Similar to the previous samples, the cathode accounts for the majority of the total cell weight in reference Sample No.7 (RELX). The cathode material content is represented by 39.0% of total cell weight and 5.1% of total weight corresponds to Al collector (Figure 9a). The anode material is represented by 20.7% of the total cell weight, while 11.8% of the total weight corresponds to the Cu collector. Separator corresponds to 6.2 % and plastic parts about 0.8 % of total weight. Electrolyte content was determined to be 6.9 %. The outer casing composed of Al foil is represented by 4.8 %.

Figure 9b shows an SEM image of a cross-section through the cathode of Sample No.7 (RELX). In **Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.** two types of grains can be observed: perfectly rounded LCO grains and smaller NMC grains. The NMC grains are porous and lack uniformity around the edges, unlike the LCO grains. The cathode material is most likely a blend of NMC 532 and pure LCO in approximate weight distribution of 50% NMC and 50% LCO. EDS analysis of the cathode cross-section revealed that the cathode material contains 14.9 % Mn (Figure 9d), 39.6 % Co (Figure 9c), and 13.6 % Ni (Figure 9e). The weight distribution in the cathode material corresponds to 0.395 g of Mn, 1.052 g of Co, and 0.361 g of Ni. The EDS analysis also showed 0.5 % of W and 1.2 % of Ti, which can be associated with contamination from the manufacturing process. The remaining cathode material consists of carbon, oxygen, and electrolyte residues.

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Figure 9. (a) Bill of material of Sample No.7 cell, (b) SEM image of cathode material - cross-sectional view, (c) EDS image of Cobalt, (d) EDS image of Manganese, (e) EDS image of Nickel

Table 2 shows the weight content of the individual metals and carbon in the analysed batteries. Since EDS spectra do not include Lithium metal, total Li content was calculated based on the known stoichiometry of cathode materials and included in Table 2. The average Li content was calculated to be 5.55% of the total battery weight on average. It is evident, that one battery is using cheap and available LMO cathode material with a small LCO additive. Other batteries

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use around 50% combination of LCO and NMC. One battery is using pure LCO as cathode material.

Table 2. The content of the elements of interest in the examined batteries.

Battery type	Cathode material [g]	Graphite [g]	Nickel [g]	Manganese [g]	Cobalt [g]	Aluminium [g]	Copper [g]	Lithium [g]
Sample No. 1 (VENIX)	4.716	2.470	0.189	2.283	0.066	0.619	1.234	0.249
Sample No. 2 (ELFBAR600)	4.639	2.495	0	0	2.783	0.491	1.231	0.258
Sample No. 3 (WAKA)	3.099	1.791	0.443	0.477	1.194	0.373	0.864	0.171
Sample No. 4 (MOTI PIIN)	1.669	1.827	0.228	0.253	0.661	0.794	0.681	0.091
Sample No. 5 (SALT)	2.797	1.654	0.674	0.747	0.459	0.403	0.787	0.163
Sample No. 6 (LIO NANO)	2.968	1.819	0.549	0.338	0.896	0.445	0.847	0.172
Average	3.315	2.009	0.347	0.683	1.010	0.521	0.940	0.184

In the Czech Republic, there are 2,232,868 smokers over the age of 15 years (24.6%).^{[4][6]} Out of these smokers, 1,007,514 also smoke e-cigarettes, representing 11.1%.^[4] Among the e-cigarette users, 45% smoke single-use e-cigarettes both daily and occasionally (95% CI).^[4] This results in a total of 453,381 individuals who smoke single-use e-cigarettes. According to the Report on Tobacco, Nicotine, and Related Products in the Czech Republic, the average number of cigarettes consumed per capita annually in 2009-2020 was 1976.^[8] In comparison, the ‘Czech Republic in Data’ study indicates an average of 2428 cigarettes for every Czech citizen who is at least 15 years old.^[5] Furthermore, according to a cigarette manufacturer, the average consumption is up to 2604 cigarettes annually per person aged 15 and above.^[7] Considering these values, we can further conclude an average annual consumption of 2463 cigarettes per person over 15. If we take the analogy of one single-use e-cigarette and a pack of cigarettes, considering the number of smokers, then the consumption of single-use cigarettes in one year would correspond to 226,690,583 units.

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The average energy of the batteries analysed was 1.585 Wh. This suggests that 359.3 MWh of energy, in the form of batteries from single-use e-cigarettes, is wasted annually in the Czech Republic. This energy could have been utilised in other applications, such as electric vehicles. Considering an average EV battery energy of 64 kWh, it would have been thus theoretically possible to produce 5,614 EV battery packs. For context, in 2023, 6,640 electric cars were sold in the Czech Republic.^[21] Using the data from Table 2, we can thus calculate the total annual consumption of materials in e-cigarettes, which is depicted in Table 3. All these materials are listed as both strategic and critical under the EU Critical Raw Materials Act.^[22] According to statistics from collection company Ecobat, an average of 57.4% of single-use e-cigarettes end up in the regular bin and are not recycled in any way.^[13] This equates to 737.8 tonnes of strategic raw materials that are irretrievably lost just in the Czech Republic, which according to Eurostat has approximately 2.4% of the EU population.^[23] This can give us a rough idea of how much of the strategic and critical battery raw materials are being used or discarded across the EU in single-use e-cigarettes.

According to the U.S. Geological Survey, Li production in Portugal is estimated at 380 tonnes in 2023.^[24] If approximately 24.5 tonnes of Li from single-use e-cigarettes are wasted in the Czech Republic only, we are losing 6.4% of Portugal's annual production just in the Czech Republic. In 2021, the mining production of Co in Finland was 1084 tonnes, which is the only mining production of Co in operation in the EU.^[25] If we consider that approximately 85.1 tonnes of Co in single-use e-cigarettes are discarded in the Czech Republic, then approximately 7.9% of the EU domestic Co production is discarded just in the Czech Republic. According to reports from Ni mines in Finland (Kevitsaa, Talvivaara), primary Ni production in Finland, which is the largest Ni producer in the EU, was equal to 41,837 tonnes of Ni.^{[26][27]} In the Czech Republic, approximately 60.4 tonnes of Ni stored in single-use cigarettes is then thrown away.

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This amount is equivalent to approximately 0.14% of Finland's Ni production. Another significantly represented element of the cathode is Mn. According to the U.S. Geological Survey, the largest primary producers of Mn are South Africa, Gabon, and Australia, with Ukraine being the largest in Europe.^[24] Of the EU countries, only Romania mines Mn. Mn production in Romania between 2015 and 2019 averaged to 3,360 tonnes/year.^[28] Battery-grade refined Mn is then from about 75% supplied by China.^[29] The EU currently has only one battery-grade manganese project under development in the Czech Republic.^[30] Our study shows that 125.0 tonnes of Mn from single-use cigarettes are wasted in the Czech Republic alone. However, manganese is not the metal of interest for current recyclers, so the question is how much of the Mn that is not discarded in municipal waste is then recycled. The considered 125.0 tonnes then represents 3.7% of the annual Mn production in the EU. In the case of graphite, the situation is the most worrying. According to 2022 data from the U.S. Geological Survey, China produces 72% of the world's natural graphite, and in the EU only 670 tonnes of graphite have been mined in Austria and Germany.^[24] In the Czech Republic alone, approximately 261.5 tonnes of battery-grade graphite are thrown away. This amount for the Czech Republic alone corresponds to 39.0% of EU graphite production. If we assume that graphite is not currently recycled commercially, we can say that even e-cigarettes that have been thrown into the waste stream for recycling will not recycle this material. In reality, the loss is equivalent to 455.7 tonnes of graphite just in the Czech Republic, which corresponds to 68.0% of the total EU production.

Table 3. Total annual amount of wasted materials from single-use e-cigarettes.

	Average weight [kg]	Total annual consumption [kg]
Cathode	3.39×10^{-3}	768 481
Graphite	2.01×10^{-3}	455 648
Nickel	4.64×10^{-4}	105 184

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Manganese	9.61×10^{-4}	217 850
Cobalt	6.54×10^{-4}	148 256
Aluminium	4.60×10^{-4}	104 278
Copper	9.33×10^{-4}	211 502
Lithium	1.88×10^{-4}	42 618

4. Conclusion

Based on the measured data, it was found that cathode materials containing Co and Ni are predominantly used in batteries for single-use e-cigarettes. These batteries have demonstrated the capability for long-term operation, exceeding 100 cycles without a significant capacity loss. As most single-use e-cigarettes end up in municipal waste, this results in material wastage that may increase in the future with the growing popularity of these tobacco products.

The vast majority of the batteries tested contained cathode materials consisting of a mixture of NMC and LCO. There was one battery that contained pure LCO, implying a more significant environmental impact. In contrast, one of the batteries contained a cathode composed entirely of LMO, which is less detrimental to the environment and is considered one of the less critical raw materials.

According to our calculations, it was found that the total amount of raw materials wasted on single-use cigarettes within the Czech Republic could cover approximately 84.5% of all electric cars sold in the Czech Republic in 2023. Nonetheless, it is electric vehicles that are often criticized for using critical raw materials in their batteries and thus for not being environmentally friendly. And yet, electric vehicles have a lifespan of over 10 years and are under strict scrutiny, while there is a large daily consumption of single-use e-cigarettes that end up in municipal waste. There is thus an inconsistency of the conditions, and it is questionable whether the use of critical raw materials should be limited in single-use small applications such as e-cigarettes, as even a small amount of critical raw materials used in a small application can

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generate a large amount of wasted material due to the high prevalence and high consumption as is the case with single-use e-cigarettes. In almost all the elements used in anodes and cathodes, just from the discarded materials in the Czech Republic, where 2.4% of the EU population lives, we would be able to cover higher units of the EU production of these elements and in the case of graphite, which is additionally in battery grade quality, we would be able to cover almost 70% of the current EU production. Disposable cigarette-type applications thus not only create costs associated with impacts on the health of the population but completely ignore the need to create a circular industry within the EU for critical and strategic battery materials. Based on our findings, we can conclude that if we were to be able to use materials that are discarded in single-use cigarettes in the EU countries, we would obtain in most cases (Mn, Co, Li, graphite) multiples of the current European production of these materials.

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A waste of critical raw materials! Secondary lithium-ion cells are being used in single-use e-cigarettes. This leads to a waste of critical and strategic raw materials. In the Czech Republic, 57.4% of single-use e-cigarettes consumed annually end up in the trash. This results in the waste of materials potentially suitable for the production of approximately 5,614 batteries for electric vehicles, in the Czech Republic alone.

